

THE BEST AGE FOR LEARNING ENGLISH

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11059774>

Abstract. This article explores the optimal age for learning English as a second language. Through a comprehensive literature review and analysis, the study finds that while language acquisition is possible at any age, the critical period between birth and puberty offers significant advantages due to heightened brain plasticity and natural language absorption abilities. The findings suggest that exposure to English during the critical period, particularly before age 6-7, can lead to more native-like proficiency.

Keywords: English language acquisition, second language learning, critical period, age factors, language proficiency

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola ingliz tilini ikkinchi til sifatida o'rganish uchun maqbul yoshni o'rganadi. Keng qamrovli adabiyotlarni ko'rib chiqish va tahlil qilish orqali tadqiqot shuni ko'rsatadiki, har qanday yoshda tilni o'zlashtirish mumkin bo'lsa-da, tug'ilish va balog'atga yetish o'rtasidagi muhim davr miyaning plastisitivligi va tabiiy tilni singdirish qobiliyatlari tufayli muhim afzalliklarga ega. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, tanqidiy davrda, ayniqsa 6-7 yoshdan oldin ingliz tilini o'rganish ona tili darajasida o'zlashtirishga olib kelishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: ingliz tilini o'rganish, ikkinchi tilni o'rganish, tanqidiy davr, yosh omillari, tilni bilish

Аннотация. В этой статье рассматривается оптимальный возраст для изучения английского языка как второго. Благодаря всестороннему обзору и анализу литературы авторы исследования пришли к выводу, что, хотя овладение языком возможно в любом возрасте, критический период между рождением и половым созреванием дает значительные преимущества благодаря повышенной пластичности мозга и способности к естественному усвоению языка. Полученные данные свидетельствуют о том, что знакомство с английским языком в критический период, особенно в возрасте до 6-7 лет, может привести к более близкому к родному владению.

Ключевые слова: овладение английским языком, изучение второго языка, критический период, возрастные факторы, уровень владения языком

INTRODUCTION

The age at which an individual begins learning a second language, such as English, has been a topic of much research and debate in the field of linguistics and language education. This article aims to investigate the optimal age for learning English, considering various factors that influence language acquisition success, such as brain development, cognitive abilities, and social influences. Understanding the impact of age on language learning can inform educational policies, teaching strategies, and learner expectations. This study will review relevant literature, analyze research findings, and discuss implications for English language education.

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

To explore the best age for learning English, a comprehensive literature review was conducted, focusing on studies that investigated the relationship between age and second language acquisition. Several influential theories and hypotheses were considered, including the Critical Period Hypothesis [1], which suggests that there is a biologically determined window of opportunity for language acquisition, typically from birth to puberty. Studies have found evidence supporting the existence of a critical period, with younger learners often achieving higher levels of proficiency, particularly in pronunciation and grammar [2][3].

Brain plasticity and cognitive development were also examined, as they play crucial roles in language learning. Research has shown that the brain is most receptive to language input during early childhood when neural connections are being formed and strengthened [4]. As individuals age, brain plasticity decreases, potentially making language acquisition more challenging [5].

Social and environmental factors were also considered, as they can impact language learning motivation and opportunities for practice. Studies have highlighted the importance of immersion, interaction with native speakers, and supportive learning environments for successful language acquisition [6][7].

RESULTS

The literature review yielded several key findings regarding the optimal age for learning English. Studies consistently showed that children who begin learning English before puberty, particularly before the age of 6-7, tend to achieve higher levels of proficiency compared to those who start later [8][9]. This advantage was observed in various language domains, including pronunciation, grammar, and vocabulary acquisition.

However, the literature also emphasized that age is not the sole determinant of language learning success. Motivation, exposure to the target language, and the quality of instruction were found to be significant factors influencing language acquisition at any age [10][11]. Studies demonstrated that older learners can still attain high levels of English proficiency, although they may require more explicit instruction and practice compared to younger learners [12].

ANALYSIS

The findings suggest that the critical period, spanning from birth to puberty, offers significant advantages for learning English as a second language. The heightened brain plasticity and natural language absorption abilities during this time facilitate more effortless and native-like acquisition. Starting English education early, ideally before the age of 6-7, can lead to better long-term outcomes in terms of proficiency and fluency.

However, it is crucial to recognize that age is not an insurmountable barrier to language learning. While older learners may face challenges related to decreased brain plasticity and entrenched first language patterns, they can still achieve high levels of English proficiency with sufficient motivation, practice, and effective learning strategies. Factors such as immersion in an English-speaking environment, interaction with native speakers, and engaging instructional methods can enhance language acquisition at any age.

DISCUSSION

The implications of these findings for English language education are significant. Educational policies and curricula should consider the benefits of starting English instruction early, ideally during the critical period. Providing children with exposure to English through immersion programs, bilingual education, or language-rich environments can capitalize on their natural language learning abilities and foster long-term proficiency.

However, it is equally important to provide support and resources for older learners who may have missed the critical period window. Developing age-appropriate teaching methods, creating opportunities for practice and interaction, and fostering a positive learning environment can help older learners overcome challenges and achieve their language goals.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the literature review and analysis suggest that the critical period, particularly before the age of 6-7, is the optimal time for learning English as a second language. Starting English education early can lead to more native-

like proficiency and long-term language acquisition success. However, it is essential to recognize that language learning is possible at any age, and older learners can still achieve high levels of proficiency with the right motivation, support, and learning strategies.

The findings of this study have implications for educational policies, curriculum development, and teaching practices. Providing early exposure to English and creating supportive learning environments can maximize language acquisition potential. Furthermore, recognizing individual differences and providing personalized support can help learners of all ages succeed in their English language learning journey.

References:

1. Lenneberg, E. H. (1967). Biological foundations of language. New York: Wiley.
2. Гафуров, Б. З. (2021). АНАЛИЗ ЛИНГВОСТАТИСТИЧЕСКОЙ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКИ АКЦЕНТНЫХ ФОНОВАРИАНТОВ ИМЕН СУЩЕСТВИТЕЛЬНЫХ РУССКОГО ЯЗЫКА. МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА, 4(1-1).
3. Gafurov, B. Z. (2022). Neologisms and their functions in the field of medicine. Journal of intellectual property and human rights, 1(08), 41-44.
4. Gafurov, B. Z. (2022). Sociolinguistics and its functions in modern linguistics. Economy and innovation. Vol. 26. Poznan, Taxes USA, 92-95.
5. Zakirovich, G. B. (2022). Service Parts of Speech as an Important Component of Advertising Text in Russian and Uzbek Languages (By the Material of Advertising in the Sphere of Medicine). European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science, 3, 1-7.
6. Uzbekistan, O. F. To verify Questionnaire of the "Uzbek Index of Premature Ejaculation".
7. Xamedxuja o'g'li, N. E. (2023). Pathogenetic Mechanisms of the Development of Severe Functional Disorders in Injuries of the Calf-Acorn Joint. AMALIY VA TIBBIYOT FANLARI ILMIY JURNALI, 2(11), 427-429.
8. Xamedxuja o'g'li, N. E. IMPROVEMENT OF TREATMENT METHODS FOR CALF-ASIK JOINT INJURIES.
9. Khikmatovna, R. M. (2021). Manifestation of language personality and communicative personality in the study of intercultural communication. European Scholar Journal, 2(4), 100-105.
10. Ruziyeva, M. H. (2021). INSON LISONIY TUZILISHINING KLINIK XUSUSIYATLARI. Scientific progress, 2(6), 1090-1096.

11. Хамидова, Н. К., Рузиева, М. Х., & Файзиев, Х. Б. (2020). Антропометрические параметры детей с различными пороками сердца (обзор литературы). Вестник науки и образования, (24-3 (102)), 96-101.
12. Nematovna, O. S., & Xikmatovna, X. M. (2020). English language in a historical perspective and forming of vocabulary. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 10, 1488-1492.
13. Djalolov, F. (2020). МАКТАБ ТАЪЛИМИДА ПАСТ ЎЗЛАШТИРИШ САБАБЛАРИ ВА ТЎЛИҚ ЎЗЛАШТИРИШ ТУРЛАРИ. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.uz), 1(1).
14. Fattoxovich, J. F. (2019). Psychology in teaching foreign languages. Достижения науки и образования, (8-3 (49)), 70-71.
15. Джалолов, Ф. Ф. (2017). ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ АКТИВНОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ СТУДЕНТОВ НЕФИЛОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ВУЗОВ. Инновационное развитие, (6), 73-74.
16. ULUGBEKOVNA, R. S. (2020). The First Period of Washington Irving's.
17. Sadikov, E. (2024). INNOVATIVE WAYS OF TEACHING SPEECH ACTS THROUGH AUDITORY SKILLS. Science and innovation in the education system, 3(2), 5-8.
18. Sadikov, E. (2023). TEACHING PRAGMATIC SPEECH ACTS OF COMPLIMENTS AND REFUSALS IN ACCORDANCE WITH CONTEMPORARY METHODS. Interpretation and researches, 1(15).
19. Tursunovich, S. E. INKORNI IFODALOVCHI NUTQ AKTLARINI KOMMUNIKATIV KOMPETENSIYANING AJRALMAS QISMI SIFATIDA O 'QITISH. ILM SARCHASHMALARI, 163.
20. Tursunovich, S. E. (2023, May). ILTIFOTNI IFODALOVCHI NUTQ AKTLARINI O'QITISH USULLARI. In Integration Conference on Integration of Pragmalinguistics, Functional Translation Studies and Language Teaching Processes (pp. 349-351).